

22. A peaceful plan for Britain to mobilize India to withdraw from its illegal occupation of Chinese territory - Wuhan Dunyi Tongji Plan

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22.1 The British Government's fabrication of the "MacMahon Line" problem and possible solutions

Unkind and inferior politicians like to create contradictions, conflicts, and wars frequently to prove their existence. Wise and well-meaning politicians often do their best to create opportunities for peaceful development in Britain. Currently, the UK is facing a serious debt crisis, so why not consider methods that can continuously increase income at non adversarial and no cost?

In 1927, the British published an official document collection called "The Treaty

Collection of Aykson," which included various agreements and treaties signed between India and all its neighboring countries (without any documents related to the McMahon Line).¹ In 1938, the British government inserted a series of fabricated documents about the "McMahon Line" into this book,¹ pretending it was published in 1929 and destroying the genuine book. Unexpectedly, two authentic copies of the book survived the fire, and decades later, scholars discovered them in the Harvard University Library and the Ministry of External Affairs Library in India, revealing the truth about the McMahon Line. The Aksai Chin region and "Arunachal Pradesh" are part of Chinese territory. The McMahon Line is forged. If India refuses to withdraw from this illegally occupied land, it may be branded as an "Indian bandit" in the hearts of the global public, which is very detrimental to its international image.

The UK should realize that India has a large population and there are many conflicts among different ethnic and religious groups. India is not a fair society as it was created on paper by the British, who forcefully brought together diverse populations from different regions. The Indian government cannot effectively manage such a large country and will inevitably face future division. Western investments in India today could potentially lead to sunk costs tomorrow. In leadership, whether at the national or regional level, the most important thing is to anticipate the future and delegate tasks to subordinates.

The international community should fully understand that reducing wars and avoiding the creation of refugees and immigrants in the original habitats of different ethnicities is one of the most valuable measures in maintaining world peace. Indigenous peoples' habitats are arranged by heaven itself, and it is best not to cause displacement through war. A cell forcibly assembled from various forms of life will inevitably have poor stability in its mitochondria, resulting in the inevitable rapid death of the cell. When people with different cultural backgrounds and customs suddenly coexist in one area, conflicts are inevitable, similar to organ transplantation in medicine. The use of immunosuppressive drugs is necessary every day to resist conflicts between various organs and tissues of the body.

For example, despite the daily use of immunosuppressive drugs, most lung transplant patients still die years later.² In fact, most patients who undergo organ transplantation do not need to undergo transplant surgery with a poor survival rate if they receive proper treatment. However, current Western medicine has not formed effective solutions, which has resulted in multiple immunosuppressant becoming blockbuster global bestsellers and creating huge economic benefits through drug or medical behavior changes.^{3,4} IQVIA data shows that global sales of tacrolimus in 2022 were \$2.655 billion.⁴ This has contributed significantly to the birth of two new disciplines, namely pharmacobehavioral economics and medical behavioral economics, by providing important case studies. However, it is difficult for the general public to control when medicine develops on the wrong path. The international community should pay attention to such issues, as immigration was an unstable factor that triggers regional conflicts and disputes,⁵ regardless of whether it is politically correct or not.

Couples usually have a courtship period of 1-4 years before marriage, but in

some countries, the divorce rate after marriage is still above 50%, and single-parent families have a significant negative impact on children's psychology. In some countries, the crime rate among immigrants or refugees is very high, with frequent incidents of rape or robbery, and the police find it difficult to control the situation, while the media suppress the voices of residents. If such situations persist long-term, isn't it a gross violation of the human rights of local residents? Is this a reflection of Western universal values, or the harm of values, or human rights violations?

By the way, from a biological perspective, the UK's departure from the EU is an unavoidable choice for maintaining a country's long-term stability, requiring the entire country to endure the pain.

Britain is the troublemaker in creating disputes and conflicts over this originally undisputed territory. British colonizers even unilaterally created a "Simla Treaty" on July 3, 1914, secretly moving the border control line 60 miles north.¹ If the British government can take the initiative to acknowledge its mistake and persuade India to quickly withdraw from all illegally occupied China's territory and relocate the Indian people from that region back to India within six months, China will give the British government 1.5% of the annual tax revenue from this new land for the next 15 years as a return to help implement just actions. This payment will be made once a year and will have no harm to Britain whatsoever. Of course, if Britain finds it profitable, it can also participate in investments in this region. The first five projects will be prioritized by British companies. As British investment increases, tax revenues in the region will naturally increase, and the UK government will enjoy more investment returns and more employment opportunities. British companies will also gain substantial profits. Isn't this a good method for increasing fiscal revenue for the UK? Why should the UK and China engage in confrontation?

The Chinese people are the most industrious nation in the world. When this land is recovered, the Chinese government and Chinese enterprises will undoubtedly increase their investment, and future development can always be expected. Of course, the UK can also mobilize some investors to invest in this new territory, further increasing the region's revenue. Once this new land is returned to China, it is expected that the infrastructure will be quickly developed due to China's rapid construction speed for infrastructure. This region is estimated to give rise to a star city in the west and multiple tourist areas, potentially attracting at least 10-20 million tourists annually. Due to the huge investment scale in the region, it is estimated that when China invests a large amount of funds, it will drive the global economy forward. Of course, China would welcome India's investment in the region and seek to achieve mutual benefits and promote peaceful development in the region. This is a win-win approach, so why not take action and negotiate with the Chinese government as soon as possible? As a joke, if the governments and businesses of the UK benefit from this Chinese territory, if you feel comfortable, can you grant the author a peace honor that will not be retracted due to any political bias?

If the U.K. cannot quickly mobilize India to return China's illegally stolen territory to China, and if the U.S. is interested in obtaining cost-free benefits from China, which would be conducive to increasing long-term gains and control the national

debt crisis, it may be useful to showcase America's leadership to the world.

22.2 India changed its country name to "Bharat", relinquishing all inheritance from British colonization, and should return its territory even more.

In addition, Indian media outlet Today India reported that there is a growing call to rename India as "Bharat" by amending the constitution,⁶ and insiders suggest that the central government may propose a resolution to rename the country. The Economic Times added that several leaders of the Bharatiya Janata Party, including the Chief Minister of Assam, voiced their support for changing India's name to "Bharat" on social media on the 5th. "Today India" stated that Indian Prime Minister Modi has also expressed similar views, as on August 15, 2022, he called on the country to eliminate all remnants of slavery in a speech. "It is worth noting that the plane used to transport the President, Vice President and Prime Minister is also engraved with the name 'Bharat'.⁶

Indian National Congress leader Jairam Ramesh confirmed in a social media post that the invitation letter from the Indian President's Office to the representatives of the G20 countries attending the upcoming summit on September 9th had "Bharat President" written on it, instead of the usual "President of India".⁶

The above shows that if India changes its name to "Bharat," it means abandoning all inheritance from British colonization. The intentional misplacement of the China-Indian border by the UK must be corrected, and India must unconditionally return the illegally occupied Chinese territory. If "Bharat" really means "seeker of light/knowledge," then India should unconditionally return the illegally occupied Chinese territory; otherwise, it would be no different from being a thief.

If the UN is fair and far-sighted, it should swiftly form a resolution ordering India to return all illegally occupied Chinese territories to China. This not only has an immeasurable impact on igniting and advancing global economic development to new heights, but also plays a milestone role in maintaining world peace and sustainable human development.

22.3 Symbols of the origin and formation of civilization, India should return illegally occupied Chinese territory if it hopes to belong to a civilized country.

Now, irrefutable evidence shows that Sumerian civilization, ancient Egyptian civilization, ancient Greek civilization, ancient Roman civilization, ancient Indian civilization, **Socrates, Plato, Aristotle, Ptolemy, Da Vinci, Euclid, Shakespeare and Alexander the Great are all fabricated or fictional.**⁷⁻¹⁰ Due to the accelerated spread of short videos, it is estimated that at least 300 million Chinese people are now aware of this. By following the principles of authenticity verification set by the U.S. FDA and examining serious errors in Western chronicle history, it would take about an hour, or even half an hour, for someone with a good mathematical foundation to discover that ancient Western history is fabricated. Some European scholars discovered extensive fabrications in ancient Egyptian, ancient Greek, ancient Roman, and ancient British history by Western missionaries a hundred years ago.

Since the 19th century, the academic community has regarded the appearance and formation of writing, cities, and bronze wares as important indicators of the origins of civilization.¹¹ This view is very shallow and seriously flawed. These are

merely signs of cultural and customary formation, not key indicators of the formation of civilization. Only Chinese civilization is the true origin of world civilization.¹¹ The only important indicator that can truly be called the origin of civilization is a culture and code of conduct based on the transmission of writing and customs that does not oppress the weak, is not afraid of the strong,¹² and treats others as oneself would like to be treated. This is the true sign of the birth of world civilization. It is embodied in China's Yi Jing (Book of Changes) 7,000 years ago and in the works of Confucius and Mozi between 500-400 BC. **The Book of Changes, written in ancient China 7000 years ago, clearly expresses the highly civilized state of humanity with the phrase "a virtuous person bears the weight of the world".**¹³ Therefore, China's foreign policy is not about dominating other countries but respecting them. However, this does not mean that China is afraid of plunderers. On the contrary, when faced with plunderers, Chinese soldiers will unleash extraordinary combat capabilities. If India truly wishes to be a country with a civilized tradition, it should proactively return Chinese territory and peacefully resolve the issues created by the fabricated border line imposed by Britain.

The author believes that humanity has entered the post-truth era since the 16th century. The birth of the "McMahon Line" was not only created by a group of British and British Indian government officials through the fabrication of history, destruction of evidence, and publication of fake books,¹⁴ but rather as a result of the Shimla Conference held after the British instigated the "autonomy" of Tibet.

If India does not regard the McMahon Line as fictional, the Hu stele from Emperor Han Xuandi's reign, recorded between 74 BC and 49 BC (**Fig 1**),¹⁵ states, "All that the sun and moon shine upon, and all that the rivers and seas reach, belongs to the Han land." The Book of Songs, written between the 11th and 6th centuries BC, records, "Under the whole heaven, there is nowhere that is not the king's land; along the border of the land, there is nowhere that is not ruled by the king's ministers."¹⁶ According to the aforementioned historical records, India is Chinese territory and Indians are Chinese subjects. Recently, a high school student from Wuhan claimed that a Martian communicated with him through dreams, stating that the territory from the North Return Line to the 28th parallel north latitude belongs to Pakistan, and the land adjacent to China along the 28th parallel north latitude belongs to China. If he has free time, he plans to write a book on the subject.

Fig 1. References 16. Israeli Ambassador to the United Nations Danny Danon presented the Bible at the UN Security Council, stating that it is the land deed of Israel and proof of Israel's ownership of Jerusalem in order to defend its sovereignty over the land. In response to this incident, Chinese netizens also presented evidence of China's ownership of the world.

<https://v.douyin.com/id9AFTCT/v@f.Bg 08/20 wSY:/>

22.4 Illegal occupation of Chinese territory by India and the consequences of the China-Indian war.

The territory within the so-called "McMahon Line" that India currently occupies illegally has always belonged to China historically. Considering the inconvenience of material transportation and other reasons, China withdrew its own territory after winning the China-Indian Border War in 1962.¹⁷ However, India has been provoking China for the past twenty years. In recent years, China has responded with cold weapons, resulting in casualties on both sides. If India continues to provoke, China cannot tolerate India's shameless and evil behavior. India's illegal occupation of Chinese territory has already declared a factual war against China. Chinese soldiers will no longer exercise restraint, as they have no reason to do so in their own territory. Once Chinese soldiers are injured instead of killed, cold weapons will never again be used in duels, and the situation will be beyond India's control.

First, the Chinese military is made up of righteous soldiers who have long been humiliated by the evil and greedy acts of India. After igniting their anger, they will rapidly annihilate the enemy and recapture the looted territory. The Chinese army

will fight the Indian army with a ratio of one to ten or one to a hundred, making it unstoppable.

Second, once the war begins, the Chinese military will not only annihilate a few Indian armies on the front line, as was the case in 1962. Rocket artillery, thermobaric weapons, and drones will directly eliminate the Indian army in a large area. The Indian army will soon lose its combat effectiveness and may well be completely destroyed.

Third, important military targets in India will be swiftly attacked, and most Indian Air Force bases will be targeted. It is possible that within a day, over 95% of the new aircraft on the frontline airports will lose their combat capability. The Indian Air Force may soon lose control of the Indian Ocean.

Fourth, rocket artillery, thermobaric projectiles, and drones will directly control the Siliguri Corridor, cutting off the Indian army's supply lines and retreat routes in the southern Tibet region, hindering their advance and leaving them with no way to retreat. The six northeastern states were either independent or semi-independent before the British arrived, and they were annexed by India. Several states have long been dissatisfied with India's prolonged oppression and have desired independence.

Fifth, Indian politicians and the public should fully understand that it was the British and Indians who intentionally attempted to steal Chinese territory by fabricating the McMahon Line. How can India, claiming to be an ancient civilization, act like thieves and robbers?

Doesn't India want to expand its political influence in the world? With New Delhi just 300 kilometers away from the Chinese border, long-range artillery can cover the surrounding areas, and infantry and paratroopers may directly attack the vicinity of New Delhi with overwhelming force, destroying evil and greedy politicians and people in India. If a large-scale war really breaks out, the Chinese military, infuriated by India's long-term barbaric aggression, is likely to launch a surprise attack on New Delhi on the first day of the war, before waiting for the situation to become clear, making it difficult for India to respond. India, originally a loose conglomerate forcibly assembled by the British with different customs and religious beliefs, has many states waiting for an opportunity to become independent countries. Under such circumstances, India will quickly break up into more than ten countries.

Sixth, the large amount of weapons and equipment left behind by the defeated Indian army is likely to fall into the hands of the people in regions hoping to break away. Once these regions are armed, the situation of India's split into multiple countries will become irreversible.

Seventh, the Chinese military will not fight alone; the people of Kashmir and Pakistan will undoubtedly take the opportunity to resist India, leading to India's complete split and economic collapse. India's dream of being a great power will shatter in one to two weeks.

Eighth, nuclear weapons are only a deterrent; India dare not use them. Once India does dare to use them, the country will be completely annihilated. India should view the illegal occupation of Chinese territory with wisdom; greed will only lead to India's destruction.

Ninth, India should prioritize morality among its domestic people, and its leaders should have a historical perspective rather than being shortsighted. They should not like to invade the human body like the COVID-19 virus. In the end, not only does the virus mutate continuously, but it is ultimately eradicated by the human body with just measures.

Tenth, if India portrays itself globally as a nation that illegally steals and robs the property of other people or countries for pleasure, any nation that fundamentally relies on theft and plunder of property will ultimately perish.

Eleven, with the development of short videos, more and more people know that India is a greedy country; in 1975, India even deposed the King of Sikkim and officially merged the sovereign nation of Sikkim into India,¹⁸⁻²¹ making it a state of India. Once India loses again, it will become a greedy joke.

Twelfth, in the last decade or so, certain things have spread and many people around the world are aware that Indians are fond of lying. The McMahon Line is obviously a fabrication, and if India's deceitful land grabbing leads to their defeat in battle, they will only become a global joke.

Thirteenth, in 1962, during the war against India's invasion, China voluntarily withdrew its troops after achieving victory. Although Chinese soldiers did confiscate a significant number of Indian weapons, including five aircraft, 437 vehicles, 631 light and heavy machine guns, 5772 rifles, 313 mortars, 13 howitzers, 36 grenade launchers, and 112 rocket launchers, these weapons were ultimately returned to India.¹⁷ This unprecedented act in the history of international warfare demonstrates China's consistent position of seeking peaceful negotiations to resolve border issues, opposing any attempt to change the border status quo by force. It shows that China is a promoter of peace while also indicating that China is not afraid of defensive wars. China disdainfully rejects the British and Indian fabrication of the Sino-Indian border and their attempts to encroach on Chinese territory. If India does not want to be identified as a thief in the international community, it should fully understand this point.

Fourteenth, The Indian government considers Gandhi as the father of the nation; however, Gandhi's principle of nonviolent non-cooperation, the foundation of India's nationhood, contradicts India's use of force to seize the territory of other countries. Does this not imply that mean they do not truly regard him as the father of the nation?

From the perspective of the metrological historical ethics, metrological political party ethics, metrological government ethics, and metrological media ethics measurement,^{22,23} the use of lies by the Indian people to occupy Chinese territory is a very ugly behavior. History will record this data and fact, and will conduct various mathematical and statistical analyses.

India should face the serious consequences caused by lies. A Japanese person once wrote an article on why Indians tend to lie, as Indians themselves have told him that their parents educate them that one's mouth has two functions - eating and lying (**Fig 2., Fig 3.**).²⁴ In their consciousness, these two elements are essential for survival. If you understand the Chinese screenshot of the article, please refer to the

original text. Additionally, there are also online videos discussing why Indians enjoy lying.²⁵⁻³⁰

Fig 2. Screenshot A. References 24.You're really wasting your life. September 14, 2022. <https://www.wenmi.com/article/pxtl8b03awos.html>

他再一次露出了满口的白牙：“是啊。我真是无法理解，你们日本人为什么会在填饱肚子这件事上费尽心思呢？我觉得日本人和中国人在做菜方面简直就是一模一样！以前，我在上海的一家印度料理店打工，偶尔去外面吃中国菜，我发现中国人也喜欢把菜做得奢华绚烂。这到底是为什么呢？”

我再次愕然。因为在我的印象中，日本人和中国人有着很大的区别。于是，我追问道：“那在其他的方面，日本人和中国人还有相似的地方吗？”

“在‘不说谎’这个方面也很像。我的父母一直教育我说‘人之所以有一张嘴，一是为了吃饭，二是为了说谎’。所以在我的意识中，吃饭和说谎是一个人能够活下去的两大要素。可是，日本人和中国人竟然从小就被教育说‘说谎是不对的’！”

我完全说不出话了，只能听他继续说下去。

“日本人和中国人最相似的地方就是‘过于认真’。印度人认为人生不过就是一场游戏，而日本人和中国人做梦都想着飞黄腾达、大富大贵。印度人在垂暮之年开始惬意地思考来生，而日本人和中国人在临死之前还在想着赚钱。”

原来如此呢。但是印度不也拥有强大的军队、核武器吗？

“你说的这种印度人只是印度12亿人口中的极少一部分，剩下的绝大多数印度人都在游戏人生一吃咖喱、午睡、看电影、跳舞、睡觉一如此反复，乐此不疲。人类不同于大象等动物的地方在于，人类可以玩耍，可以享乐。但是日本人和中国人竟然认真到了近乎死板的地步，你们真是在浪费人生啊！”

Fig 3. Screenshot B. References 24.You're really wasting your life. September 14, 2022. <https://www.wenmi.com/article/pxtl8b03awos.html>

22.5 Cooperation and Reconciliation between China, Britain and India during World War II

Britain's High Commissioner to India, Sir Dominic Asquith, had called for a peaceful resolution between India and China on August 24, 2017, but stated that the UK, as a third party, would not intervene in the dispute.³¹ I believe that this approach by the UK is highly unwise. Over the past two centuries, the United Kingdom has been involved in creating conflicts and wars in various regions of the world. If the UK government really wants to be a promoter of peace, it should proactively rectify its past mistakes and urge the Indian military to withdraw completely from the illegally occupied Chinese territories and address all related consequences appropriately. Should China engage in another counter-aggression war against India, it will undoubtedly deal a heavy blow to India, reclaiming the unlawfully occupied territories. India will inevitably face internal divisions and may even split into more than a dozen countries, losing its capability for aggression.

By the time the situation is resolved, the UK will not only gain no political benefits, but also be unable to reap any economic gains from China without any cost. Additionally, when evaluated from the perspective of military ethics and political ethics in future history, considering the wicked contribution of the UK in the India-Pakistan conflict, the UK will become the world's leading nation habituated to creating potential wars. British politicians will be branded as experts in generating potential wars and will perpetually be held in shame in the annals of history.

Objectively speaking, there have been successful examples of cooperation between China and the UK in international affairs. During World War II, in April 1942, the Chinese Expeditionary Forces achieved a miracle when the Japanese aggressively advanced towards Mandalay. In the Battle of Imphal in Western Burma, with only 1121 troops,^{32,33} the Chinese Expeditionary Forces defeated over 4,000 Japanese soldiers, saving the besieged First Burma Division of the British-Indian Army composed of over 7,000 personnel and blocking the Japanese advance towards India.

If British politicians can wisely recognize the immorality of the virus left behind by decades of British-Indian collaboration, which continues to undermine world peace, the UK should adopt a friendly stance to mediate the India-China border issue. It should publicly declare that previous documents regarding the India-China border were fabricated and urge India to resolve this issue on the basis of historical facts by withdrawing from the illegally occupied Chinese territories. If successful, British politicians will contribute a new example for the resolution of territorial disputes for international peace, and the Nobel Peace Prize of the future may beckon to British politicians.

In September of this year, Birmingham, the UK's second largest city, went bankrupt overnight.³⁴ If Birmingham wants to save the city's economy, it can seize the opportunity alone, consult with the Chinese government, and urge the UK to publicly release relevant statements, admit that the UK has forged the China-India

border in the past, and communicate with India. If the mayor of Birmingham manages to successfully mediate this issue, the future Nobel Peace Prize could be beckoning towards the mayor.

Moreover, if the UK believes that China's lending to build high-speed railways for other countries poses a threat to Western values, then China may consider stopping promoting the concept. In the future, unless the country itself provides funding, China will only participate in high-speed rail or railway construction. China will not provide loans to prevent Western countries from worrying about China's growing influence and threats. If politicians in the UK believe that these terms of exchange are reasonable, when the UK fully resolves the issue of the fake Sino-Indian border line that it has fabricated in the past, it is believed that China will make a commitment to this issue. UK statesmen may achieve a visibly dominant position in the world.

22.6 The second son and descendants of God were born in China, should believers of the Bible and the United Kingdom remain silent about the lies of believers and non-believers?

Hong Xiuquan, the Heavenly King of Taiping Heavenly Kingdom in China, was proven to be the second son of God and the brother of Jesus. This was verified by the Roman Catholic Church and personally authenticated by the Pope,³⁵ who sent representatives to China for this purpose. God has no other descendants in the world, but the second son of God, Hong Xiuquan, still has descendants in China, who should have the right to inherit. If believers of the Bible do not support China's claims and territorial integrity, would they not be going against the will of God? Would they not be deceiving God? When the Prime Ministers and Presidents of the United Kingdom and the United States take their oaths of office, don't they place their hands on the Bible? Why do believers in the United Kingdom, the United States, Europe, and around the world not respect God? If you still have faith in the Bible.

The descendants of God are in China, which may come as a surprise, but this has been personally endorsed by the Holy See and the Pope. Isn't this God's will, requiring followers worldwide to respect China's rightful claims? If you believe in God, that is.

Finally, it should be pointed out that the international community must adhere to a good moral order in order to sustain development. Just like how a person stays alive because their organs function well, if the functions weaken to the extreme or are severely impacted by external forces, death is inevitable. If the forceful annexation of Sikkim by India is considered legal, then can't the United States or Russia also use force to annex India legally? The United Nations failed to play any restraining role in India's annexation of a small country like Sikkim, which completely damaged the image of the United Nations. Shouldn't the United Nations reconsider this matter? India's forcible annexation of a country seriously disrupts world peace and also damages the global leadership image of the United States, which ranks second to India. Can the Nobel Peace Prize be awarded to a country that does not change its image of disrupting world peace?

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